

TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT OF EFFECTIVENESS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCES IN NGAPATTINAM DISTRICT OF TAMILNADU

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Abstract

Television plays an important role in the development of the country. In most of the developed countries, people are well aware of the advantages of television. They are getting update information through television. In India, radio and newspaper played a major role earlier in providing information to the people. The accessibility of television has brought about tremendous changes in the attitudes of people, both urban as well as rural. Presently, they are getting the latest information on practically every aspect of life, literature and science with the help of television network. Urban and rural people have changed their attitudes towards social, economic and political matters due to their exposure to this powerful medium. The mass media has created demand for goods and services in rural areas. Smart marketers are employing the mix of conventional and non-conventional media to create demand for their products. The growth of satellite TV channels and cable TVs has had a major impact on rural consumers. It has led to change in lifestyles. Consumption of non food items has increased. Since the accessibility to television is high compared to other media, rural consumers now aspire to buy well known, popular brands rather than we purchase commodities.

Keywords : Television, media, channels, cable, Social

INTRODUCTION

Advertising, as it today, was not used until about 200 years ago. Although Americans the forerunners of modern advertising, it has its roots in England. The Industrial Revolution led to the expansion of mass manufactured goods in Europe and America making markets larger and larger. Localized markets were replaced by extended domestic national markets and international markets. This development altered the relationship between the maker and the user of goods, and created a need for advertising. The need for communication increased because of the mechanization of mass production and it is the advertising, which has provided this vehicle of communication. The development of the modern advertising agency system was quality significant, for it has helped advertising to become an institution and a profession.

In the early part of the 20th century, advertising form underwent metamorphosis. This was possible because of the phenomenal growth of such media as television, radio and cinema, in addition to the large number of new products introduced as a result of the industrialization and economic development of the country. Artificial intelligence of 6th generation computers will add a new dimension to advertising and its planning. Indian advertising has no doubt registered a rapid growth and has acquired a certain amount of professional character. But, by and large, it still appears to be in a shambles, unable to attract the best managerial talent, apart from being administratively weak and unable to devise a self-regulatory mechanism, which is necessary if it is to register professional growth and play a useful role in the socio-economic development of the country.

Indian advertising has yet to shed its elitist urban and open up the vast rural market which, in per capita terms, may be poor but which in the aggregate, is an important market segment as 70 to 80 percent of the Indian population resides in villages, to which advertising has not yet spread to the desired extent. Besides this, it has a great role to play in assisting in the eradication of poverty, for 46 percent of our population lives below the poverty line; in communicating the availability of goods, services and opportunities; and in contributing to improvements in living standards.

2.REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Vijaykumari (1999),1 in her study “**Effectiveness of advertising with reference to television and print media**” analyzed the effectiveness of two popular advertisement media viz. print and television and their impact on people. The researcher concluded that the television advertisement has given more impact than advertisement in print media on the people in their buying decisions, because it has the audio and visual medium and it attracted viewers easily.

P.Akbarbatcha(2001)2 in his study entitled “**Advertising industry-with special reference to print media intermediaries**” analyzed the public opinion towards advertisement in the print media. The researcher has attempted a specific study with reference to print media and concluded that the print media played a vital role in the minds of the middle class people.

Jacob Goldenberg et.al.(2002)3 in their article “**How cross market communication can create a major slump to sales**” analyzed the effect of the parameters of communication across the early and main markets on saddle prevalence. The cross-market communication parameters have a considerable influence in determining the existence of saddle. In a narrow range of relatively low values of the cross-market communications parameters, there is no clear cut relationship between the values of their parameters and the existence of saddle.

K.S.Sujit et al (2003)4 in their article, “**Liberalization and advertisement intensity in India public limited companies**” concluded that the Indian public companies have gone up after the introduction of liberalization. This is due to the liberalization policy and an increasing role of market mechanism. Market mechanism leads to opening up of industries and brings competitiveness and hence firms try to maintain their market shares through advertisement.

3.STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the present globalised scenario, companies operating in India will have only two options either to go global or go rural. The cost going global is very high and it is difficult to gauge marketing in other countries. It is better to target the rural market as it growing day by day. Rural India is emerging as a large market for number of goods and services- financial services, health care and education, and telecommunication. The growing reach of the electronic media has created a huge change in the life style of rural consumers because of television programs and its advertisements.

Whatever the reasons against testing advertising effectiveness, two things are certain- one, that advertising has become a potent tool for increasing sales, and, second, that large sums of money are spent on it. Since each advertisement is a costly affair, the object is to minimize the possibility of costly mistakes in terms of poor advertisements, which not only cost money to a firm but which results in losing opportunities for pushing and selling extra quantities of the product, or in the loss of market to the competitor . Advertisement testing may be done either before or after the advertisement has run in the media. The first one is referred to as pre- testing, and the other one is referred to as post testing. However, the basic purpose of testing advertisement is to avoid costly mistakes, to predict the relative strength of alternative advertising strategies, and to increase its efficiency. Hence, the problem of the study lies in the process of evaluating the effectiveness of the TV advertisements in Nagapattinam district.

4.AREA OF THE STUDY

The area of the study has been limited to the district of Nagapattinam only, which is a part in the Granary of south India and the Rice bowl of Tamil Nadu. It is an important coastal district in Cauvery delta of eastern Tamil Nadu. It was carved out by bifurcating the composite Thanjavur district on 18.10.1991. This District is predominantly, A coastal District having a large coast line of 141 kilometres. This District has a numerous places of historical importance. Nagapattinam is an old port Town. This District is having an area of 2715.83 sq.kms in its fold. This District Headquarters is Nagapattinam. This district is enveloping 11 panchayat unions, 4 Municipalities, 8 Town Panchayats on its development side. On the revenue side, it is housing 2 revenue rdivisions with 4 and 3 Taluks respectively and 523 revenue villages. Decades back to sangam- age, NAGAPATTINAM district was ruled over by Chola Kings and by pandiyas for a short while. On the economic front, tourism plays a key role in the economy of the district, even though the main stay of the people id agriculture and fishing, Paddy and sugarcane are the staple crops. The Cauvery is the major source of irrigation. As the proverb goes “Indian agriculture is agamble on the monsoon” the agriculture in the district is monsoon oriented and when monsoon fails agriculture is adversely affected. There is not much industrial activity as it is predominantly an agricultural district on the east coast. In Nagapattinam district, even farming and fishing is still a subsistence attempt and not a commercial venture. Majority of the people in the district are either seasonally unemployed or under employed. In spite of

several Government schemes, nothing substantial has been achieved both in agriculture and in fishing in the District. Therefore, it is worth studying in the District.

5.OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The Objectives of the study are

1. To study the growth and development of television advertisements and markets in India.
2. To analyze the awareness of people towards advertisements in television.
3. To identify the factors influencing the people through television advertisements in the selection of products and services.
4. To examine the level of changes made by advertisements in television on the socioeconomic conditions of the rural people.
5. To analyze the level of satisfaction of the people towards information provided by advertisements in television.

6.HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Several hypotheses were framed in the course of completing the study for evaluating the effectiveness of the TV advertisements. The hypotheses were tested with the help of suitable statistical techniques like Chi-square test, and F-test ANOVA and the inferences derived from the interpretations were accepted or rejected accordingly. The hypotheses used in the study are;

There is no significant difference between the mean scores on the programmes ranked in television among the respondents

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of the factors influencing the respondents through TV advertisements in selecting product and service.

There is no significant difference between the mean scores on the level of change made by advertisements in televisions on their socio-economic conditions of the respondents and their age groups.

There is no significant difference between the mean score on level of changes made by TV advertisement on socio-economic of respondents and their Annual income.

There is no significant difference between the mean scores on the level of satisfaction towards information provided by advertisements in televisions and the age groups of the respondents.

7.RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Study is descriptive in nature. Survey method was adopted to carry out the objectives of the study. Both primary and secondary data were used in the study.

7.1 Sample selection

In Nagapattinam district, there are 2 Revenue divisions, 8 Taluks, 4 Municipalities, 11 panchayats and 434 panchayats with 2,508 Habitations. There are 2,71,827 rural households and

71,786 urban households. The total population of the district according to 2011 census is 14.88 lakhs, of which 11.58 lakhs reside in rural areas. Out of 434 Panchayats, 50 Panchayats were selected at random giving due coverage to all the 11 Panchayat unions. In each village, 10 television viewers who have attained the age of 18 years and above were selected at random. Only one viewer was selected from one household to avoid duplication of responses. Thus, a total of 500 television viewers were selected conveniently by using multi stage random sampling technique.

7.2 Sources of the data

The List of Panchayats available in the District collector's office was used as the source to select the sample Panchayats and Record of Households in the Village Administrative Office was used as the source to select the sample TV viewers.

7.3 Date Collection

Secondary data were collected from a wide spectrum of sources such as related books, relevant magazines, Published and unpublished sources and Government reports. Websites of various organizations and Advertising agencies were also of great use in the collection of Secondary data. The Primary data were collected from Television viewers of the district by conducting sample survey using structured, pre-tested interview schedule, adopting convenience sampling model.

7.4 Data Collection Tools

A well structured interview schedule was administered in this study to elicit information from the sample TV viewers. The interview Schedule was pretested with fifty respondents and based on the results obtained, it was slightly modified.

7.5 Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The data thus collected were classified, tabulated, analysed and interpreted with the help of relevant statistical tools making use of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). Simple Percentage, Weighted Average Analysis, Factor Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis were put to use in analyzing the data. Charts, diagrams and graphs were also in this study to simplify the data and to facilitate easy understanding.

8. Findings of the study

The researcher observed the following results in his attempt to evaluate the Effectiveness of advertisements in Television in Nagapattinam district.

Age Wise Distribution out of 500 respondents, 17.2 percent respondent are in the age group below 20 years. 29.4 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 20-40 years; 34.6 percent respondents are in the age group of 40-60 years and the remaining 18.8 percent of them are in the age group of above 60 years. As much as 64 percent of the respondents are in the age groups of 20-60 years.

Annual income of the 500 respondents, as much as 29 percent of them were in the annual income group of RS.60,000-1,20,000. The respondents in the other income groups were equally

distributed around 16 to 18 percent. Majority of the respondents of the study belong to middle income group with an annual income of Rs.1,20,000-2,40,000.

The weighted average analysis reveals that news in television has scored the maximum and stood at first rank followed by movies and songs in the second ranks. Serial programs stood at third rank, sports at fourth rank, agriculture at fifth rank, advertisement at sixth and other programs at seventh rank.

The weighted average score reveals that out of 6 features of TV advertisement, 4 features scored more than the average and only 2 features scored just below the average. Therefore, it can be concluded that the advertisements in Television are significantly effective in the study area.

Number of advertisements remembered in a day 500 respondents, 36.6 percent of the respondents remembered only two TV advertisements they have seen in a particular day, 48.2 percent of the respondents remembered four TV advertisements, 11.4 percent of the respondents remembered six TV advertisements and 3.8 percent of the respondents remembered more than ten TV advertisements. Majority of the respondents i.e. 48.2 percent remembered four TV advertisements.

9.Suggestions of the study

Like market segmentation TV Advertisements are also require segmentation based on Geographical, Demographical, Socio-physiological and product basis so that advertisements can reach the targeting group and fulfil their requirements.

There are separate channels for Sports, News, Music, Cinema etc., likewise separate channels for advertisements can be introduced. It will create easy access for people to advertisements.

Advertisements on service sector, like Banking, mutual fund, Health care, EDUCATION, Employment, Matrimonial may be improved. This can be done by introducing separate channels for advertising.

The cost of telecasting advertisements is very high as it is determined on the basis of Television Rating points. This can be reduced considerably for establishing separate channels for advertising.

Introducing separate channels for advertising will induce the people to see the advertisements whatever they require information about the product without compulsion.

10.CONCLUSION

To conclude, the results of the opinion survey conducted in Nagapattinam District to evaluate the effectiveness of TV Advertisements reveal that the TV Advertisements are effective as they provide necessary information about the products and services to the public and influence them highly in their buying decisions. It also help them to change their socio economic conditions.

It can be said that effectiveness of TV Advertisements in India should be measured in its contribution towards providing impetus for educational, cultural, economic, social, political and

development projects in the country and not just by growth in the number of TV Advertisement or the so-called choice available to the viewers. India may not be a poor country, but it is a country with millions of poor people. Television advertisements as one of the most ubiquitous elements of modern life, it should not favors the corporate sector only but it must also make the country aware of this ‘other’ segment of the population so that they do not fade away from national consciousness, and steps are taken to address then poverty and the accentuating inequalities in our society by extending relevant information about the products and services to the poor through advertisements.

11.LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Keeping in view the limitations of an individual researcher, the study has been confined to advertisements of the TV media only. The other media were kept out of the purview of the study because of their peculiar nature.

Moreover, in order to make the study intensive and purposeful, it has been limited to the district of Nagapattinam only, which is an economically backward district in the eastern coastal Tamil Nadu. The results of the study cannot be generalizes and applied to other areas of the state or the country due to demographical factors.

TABLE 1.1
Age wise distribution of the Respondents

Age Group	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Below 20 years	86	17.2
20-40 years	147	29.4
40-60 years	173	34.6
Above 60 years	64	18.8
Total	500	100

Source: Primary Data

TABLE 1.2
Gender wise classification of the Respondents

Gender	No.of Respondents	Percentage
Male	254	50.6
Female	246	49.2
Total	500	100

Source: Primary Data

TABLE 1.3

Number of Television channels watched in a day

Number of Channels	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Only 2	113	22.6
2-4	205	41.0
4-6	135	27.0
6-8	21	4.2
8 and more	26	5.2
Total	500	100

Source: Primary Data

TABLE 1.4

Hours Spent on Watching Television in a Day

Number of Hours Spent	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Less than 2 hours	133	26.6
2-4 hours	217	43.4
4-6 hours	123	24.6
6 hours and above	27	5.4
Total	500	100

Source: Primary Data

REFERENCES

BOOKS

1. **Chunawalla S.A, Advertising Sales and promotion Management**, Himalaya Publishing House, Delhi,2006.
2. Gupata S.P, **Statistical Methods**, Sultan Chand and Sons, New Delhi,2002.
3. Kenneth E.Clow and Donald Baack, **Integrated Advertising and Promotion, and Marketing Communication**, Person Pearson prentice Hall, Delhi.,2007
4. Kothary.C.R. **Research Methodology Methods and Techniques**, New Age International Publications, Chennai 2007.
5. Krishnamcharyulu,C.S.G. and Lolita Ramakrishna, **Rural Marketing Text and Cases**, Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt Ltd., Delhi,2006.

JOURNALS

1. Amitjain et al., “ **Distribution and Retailing Trends in Rural Markets**”, Indian Journal of Marketing Vol.xxv,No,6, September 2005, PP.11-15.
2. Amit Kumar Sinha, “**Gender Difference among Adolescents as Influencers and Impact of Communication in the Family Purchase Decision.**” The ICFAL Journal of Marketing Management Volume IV No.4, November

3. Anil Chandhok et al., “Creativity a Strategy to Successful Advertising”, Advertising Express, Vol. Viii, No 11, November 2008,pp,21-23
4. Arien Strashiem et al., “Psychometric Properties of the Schlinger Viewer Response Profile (VRP)”, Journal of Advertising Services at Vol.36, No.4, No.4, Winter 2007, PP.101-112
5. Ashih Points, “ TV Scrolling Services at Doordharshan, Vol 11.No.2 June 2007, PP.65-70,
6. John Gabriel.s “The Impact of Television Advertisement on Youth”, The ICFAI Journal of Marketing Management, Vol.No.3, November 2006, P.70.7.
7. Judith a. Garretson et al., “ The Role of Spokes Characters as Advertisement and cues in Integrated Marketing Communications,” Journal of Marketing, Volume 69, No.4, October-2005, PP.118-132
8. Roopa K.C Effectiveness of Television Advertisements in Nagapattinam, “Bharathidasan University” Vol.2 April 2013